

Synthesis and study of electrophysical properties of the $ZnCe_2Se_4$ compound

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Abstract: In this work, a new $ZnCe_2Se_4$ ternary chalcogenide compound was synthesized and its electrophysical properties were systematically investigated in the temperature range of 300–900 K. The compound was prepared by a high-temperature solid-state reaction using stoichiometric amounts of high-purity initial components to ensure phase stability and compositional homogeneity. The electrical conductivity, thermoelectric power (Seebeck coefficient), Hall coefficient, and Hall conductivity were measured to analyze the charge transport mechanisms and carrier characteristics. The temperature dependence of electrical conductivity showed typical semiconducting behavior, with conductivity increasing as temperature increased, indicating a thermally activated transport process. Based on the Arrhenius relationship between $\ln\sigma$ and $1/T$, the width of the forbidden band was calculated from the slope of the linear region. The band gap energy was determined to be $\Delta E = 1.97$ eV, suggesting that $ZnCe_2Se_4$ belongs to the class of wide-band-gap semiconductors and may operate effectively at elevated temperatures. The type of conductivity was established from the sign of the Hall coefficient and the temperature dependence of the thermoelectric power. The Hall coefficient remained negative throughout the studied temperature interval, and the thermoelectric potential confirmed the dominance of electrons as charge carriers. Therefore, $ZnCe_2Se_4$ exhibits stable n-type conductivity in the entire investigated range. The obtained results indicate that this compound is a promising material for high-temperature semiconductor and optoelectronic applications.

Keywords: Rare earth elements, semiconductor, temperature phase, complex methods, X-ray phase analysis, microstructural analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chalcogen semiconductors are widely used crystals in solid-state physics. These crystals have a wide range of practical applications. In recent decades, the transition from binary compounds to ternary compounds in semiconductor materials science has been rapidly progressing. These compounds allow obtaining materials with highly effective properties for use in various fields of science and technology. Such materials are widely used in quantum electronics, laser technology, and optoelectronics. Due to the unique and unique structure of ternary semiconductor compounds, the application of various compounds doped with rare earth elements has recently attracted great interest. Studies conducted over the past few years have shown that the introduction of rare earth element (NTE) ions, such as Cerium (Ce), into the matrix of materials leads to partial mutual transmission of 4f electrons screened (protected) by the 5s and 5p layers, as a result of which quite pronounced optical transitions appear in the 4f layer itself. It is known that the change in physical properties is primarily related to the crystal structure. Therefore, the study of the electronic and crystal structures of the compound is important for explaining the physical properties of these materials.

The development of new generation high-efficiency semiconductor materials is one of the most important issues in modern materials science (1). In the production of such materials, complex compounds based on zinc (Zn), rare earth elements (Ln= Ce, Pr, Nd, Gd, Sm, Yb, Er, etc.) and sulfur (S), selenium (Se) and tellurium (Te) occupy a special place (2). These types of compounds are obtained by direct method in 2 ways. It is obtained from elements of special purity taken in stoichiometric composition and binary chalcogen compounds of zinc and rare earth elements.

Zinc selenide (ZnSe) is an important group II-VI chalcogenide semiconductor. Like many other II-VI group semiconductors, research on the synthesis and growth of cyanic selenium (ZnSe) is gaining great attention due to the improvement of some of its properties and applications (3). ZnSe has a wide band gap of about 2.7 eV. In addition to its wide band gap, ZnSe has a large exciton binding energy (21 meV), excellent electron transport properties, high linear and nonlinear refractive indices, and good optical transparency over a wide range of the visible spectrum.

Zinc selenide (ZnSe) is a widely used semiconductor. It has the most promising wide band gap energy. Widely used in the development of short-wavelength semiconductor electronics and display systems. It has a cubic and hexagonal crystal structure. Zinc-selenium makes it promising for the production of X-ray detectors that do not require cooling. Synthesized cyanide-selenium thin films using different methods. Examples of these include thermal evaporation, electrochemical deposition, and chemical bath deposition. The type of crystal structure of zinc-selenium (ZnSe), Sphalerite lattice constant $a = 5,6686 \text{ \AA}$, Wurzite lattice constants $a = 4.01 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.54 \text{ \AA}$. Zinc selenide single crystals are mainly grown in the gas phase. In the Zn-Se system, the only compound that melts congruently at 1525°C is ZnSe. Zinc selenide is used to

make piezoelectric devices, chemical sensors, light detectors, infrared windows, blue-light emitting diodes, solar cells, etc. In addition, silk selenide is widely used in the manufacture of optical windows, lenses, mirrors, prisms, optical blanks, plates, and discs. Thus, we can say that ZnSe is considered a promising material for both spintronics and optoelectronics.

Cerium 3-selenide (Ce_2Se_3) is a narrow-bandgap semiconductor. The band gap width is approximately $\Delta E = 1.2$ eV. Ce_2Se_3 can exist in several polymorphic phases. α - Ce_2Se_3 (low temperature phase), β - Ce_2Se_3 (high temperature phase) (4-8). Ce_2Se_3 is mainly synthesized by direct method at high temperature (1000-1100°C). The synthesis is carried out in vacuum or in an inert gas (Ar, N_2) environment. The melting point is 1700°C. It can be oxidized at high temperatures to form Ce_2O_3 or CeO_2 . Cerium can exhibit paramagnetic behavior due to its 4f electrons. Ce_2Se_3 has absorption properties in the infrared (IR) region. Although Ce_2Se_3 does not have widespread industrial use, it is important for scientific and technological research. Ce_2Se_3 can be applied as a semiconductor and thermoelectric material. It has high potential for IR sensors in optoelectronics. Ce_2Se_3 is a solid and dark brown in color. The crystal structure of Ce_2Se_3 is cubic. The crystal structure can change depending on temperature. The density of Ce_2Se_3 is 5.7 g/cm³. Ce_2Se_3 is widely used as a semiconductor. (9).

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The main goal of the work is to study the nature of the interaction between zinc selenide and cerium selenide, to determine the optimal synthesis regime of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound obtained during this interaction, and to study some of the physicochemical properties of this compound. The ZnCe_2Se_4 ternary compound has been synthesized for the first time. The synthesis of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound is carried out by the direct method in the following manner.

High-purity starting components ZnSe and Ce_2Se_3 were taken in stoichiometric proportions, weighed on an analytical balance with an accuracy of 10^{-5} , and placed into a quartz ampoule. The air in the ampoule is evacuated to a pressure of about 10^{-3} – 10^{-4} mmHg, and the ampoule is sealed in the flame of an oxygen–gas torch. The synthesis of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound was carried out in a single-zone synthesis furnace positioned horizontally and capable of rotation at an angle of 180°. By moving the synthesis furnace in specific directions, it is heated up to 1000 °C. It is kept at this temperature for 4-6 hours. Then it is cooled slowly to ensure crystallization. To ensure the perfection of the crystal, it was subjected to homogenization in a muffle furnace at 900° C for 150–200 hours. The obtained dark-gray compact sample was individually studied using complex methods of physicochemical and analytical methods. X-ray phase analysis (XRD) was used to determine the crystal structure of the obtained compound, EDX/SEM was used to determine the elemental composition and morphology of the compound, BDTA-8M was used to determine the melting temperature, etc. X-ray phase analysis of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound was performed using a Bruker D8 Avance diffractometer.

The X-ray diffraction spectra of the compound ZnCe_2Se_4 are shown in Figure 1.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound measured at room temperature. The sharp and well-defined diffraction peaks confirm the formation of a crystalline ZnCe_2Se_4 phase. The absence of extra peaks indicates that the synthesized sample is predominantly single-phase.

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction spectra of the compound ZnCe_2Se_4 .

Based on the results of X-ray phase analysis, it was determined that this compound crystallizes in a cubic crystal structure. Space group $143\bar{a}$, elementary lattice parameters; $a=8.76\text{\AA}$, Elementary lattice volume $V=577.29\text{\AA}^3$, number of molecules 4, density 5.56 g/cm^3 . To clarify the results of our synthesis, X-ray phase analysis, high-temperature differential thermal analysis (HTDA), microstructure analysis (MSA), etc. were used, and the individuality of this compound (ZnCe_2Se_4) was confirmed. ZnCe_2Se_4 is a dark-gray crystalline substance. It is resistant to air and water. Only strong mineral acids break it down.

Microstructural analysis of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound. Based on the results of the analysis conducted in SEM, the homogeneity of the compound has been proven. The results of the microstructural analysis of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Crystal structure of the compound ZnCe_2S

The microhardness of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound was determined using a PMT-3 microhardness tester. The microhardness of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound is $H \mu = 220$ Mpa.

In order to determine whether the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound is a semiconductor, its electrophysical properties were investigated over a wide temperature range (300-900 K).

For this purpose, samples of the synthesized ZnCe_2Se_4 sample were prepared in cylindrical shape with a length of $l = 7-8$ mm and a diameter of 4-6 mm. Electrical parameters were measured using a DC probe method. After polishing the polycrystalline material for electrical properties, its suitability for measurement is studied under a microscope. Silver metals are used as contacts to measure the electrical conductivity of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound. The electrical conductivity and Hall constant of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound were measured in the temperature range of 300-900 K, and the results obtained are given in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. The change in electrical conductivity and Hall constant with increasing temperature is characteristic of semiconductors, as can be seen from the dependence graph $\lg \sigma \approx f(10^3/T)$ and $\lg R - f(10^3/T)$.

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound.

As can be seen from Figure 3, the specific electrical conductivity of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound decreases as the temperature increases from room temperature to 600 K, as in metals. The reason for this is that the number of free charge carriers remains constant in the indicated temperature range and the mobility decreases.

However, starting from a temperature of 600 K, the charge carriers in the valence band absorb energy equal to or greater than the width of the forbidden band and move to the conduction band, resulting in an increase in the value of electrical conductivity.

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of the Hall constant of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound.

It was found that the Hall coefficient of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound in the temperature range of 300-900 K increases with an increase in temperature from room temperature to 550 K, and decreases in the region of specific conductivity (Figure 4). In general, the temperature dependences of the specific permittivity and Hall coefficient of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound confirm each other.

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of the thermoelectric power of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound.

The temperature dependence of the thermoelectric current for the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound has been studied (Figure 5). The temperature dependence of these parameters, experimentally studied for the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound, is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen from Figure 5, an increase in α occurs in the temperature region of 300-500 K, and then a decrease.

The anomalous increase in the Hall and thermoelectric coefficients at low temperatures is most likely a result of the complex zone structure of that compound. The width of the forbidden band of the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound in the specific conductivity region, based on the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity and Hall constant, was calculated. It was found that $\Delta E = 1.97$ eV for the compound under study. The conductivity type was determined for the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound based on the change in sign of the Hall and thermoelectric currents, and it was determined that it has "n"-type conductivity in the studied temperature range.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of Hall conductivity

The electrical conductivity and thermoelectric potential can be directly explained by the temperature-dependent change in the mobility of charge carriers. This, in turn, can be associated with changes in the mobility of other parameters (α, σ) of the charge carriers of the crystal under study. The temperature dependence of the conductivity is given in Figure 6.

As can be seen, the conductivity increases at low temperatures, and decreases at high temperatures, in the specific conductivity region. This occurs according to a law close to the $T^{-2/1}$ law. This corresponds to the stretching of charge carriers by longitudinal acoustic backgrounds in the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, a novel ternary chalcogenide compound ZnCe_2Se_4 was successfully synthesized for the first time by the direct solid-state reaction method using high-purity ZnSe and Ce_2Se_3 precursors. Comprehensive structural, microstructural, and electrophysical investigations were carried out in a wide temperature range of 300–900 K to elucidate the fundamental properties of the synthesized material. X-ray diffraction analysis revealed that the ZnCe_2Se_4 compound crystallizes in a cubic crystal system and is formed predominantly as a single-phase material, indicating the high quality and phase purity of the synthesized sample. Microstructural investigations performed by SEM/EDX confirmed the compositional homogeneity and uniform distribution of constituent elements throughout the sample. The compound exhibits high chemical stability under ambient conditions and is resistant to air and moisture.

Detailed electrophysical measurements demonstrated that ZnCe_2Se_4 exhibits intrinsic semiconductor behavior.

The anomalous increase in Hall coefficient and thermoelectric power observed at lower temperatures is most likely associated with the complex electronic band structure and the presence of localized f-electron states characteristic of rare-earth-containing chalcogenides.

Overall, the obtained results indicate that ZnCe_2Se_4 is a promising wide-band-gap semiconductor material with stable electrophysical properties at elevated temperatures. These

characteristics make the compound a potential candidate for applications in high-temperature electronics, optoelectronic devices, and thermoelectric energy conversion systems.

5. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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